

Research Article

A Study to Assess the Prevalence of Urolithiasis Among the Sedentary Workers Working in Selected Areas of Vijayapura District, Karnataka

^aSankappa Gulaganji, ^bMeenaxi Madabhavi and ^cManjunath Patil

^aAssociate Professor, BLDEA's Shri B. M. Patil Institute of Nursing Sciences, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India

^bNursing Officer, Community Health Centre, Chadachan, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India

^cAssistant Professor, BLDEA's Shri B. M. Patil Institute of Nursing Sciences, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India

*Corresponding Author Email: msn.msc@gmail.com

Received: August 29, 2025

Accepted: September 21, 2025

Published: September 27, 2025

Abstract

Objective: The main objective of this study is to determine the prevalence and risk factors of urolithiasis among sedentary workers working in selected areas of Vijayapura.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted in June 2021 in Vijayapura district. Data were obtained through direct interviews with participants using an 18-question self-questionnaire, inquiring about demographic data (age, gender, weight, height, location, and occupation), educational level, history of renal stone disease (symptoms, modality of diagnosis, hospital admission, and previous treatment), and risk factors of stone formation such as family history, daily fluid intake, and type of fluid.

Results: A total of 300 individuals were interviewed. The overall percentage of those diagnosed with urolithiasis was 5.4%, including 5.6% males and 5.2% females ($P = 0.05$). Of those with stones, 4% were medically treated, 1.4% were hospitalized, and 1.1% were surgically managed for stones. There was a positive linear correlation between the prevalence of stones and participants' age group ($r = 0.87$, $P = 0.01$). More than 80% of participants were highly educated, which did not impact the prevalence of stone formation ($P = 0.12$). Urolithiasis was reported by 7.4% of obese participants, 4.8% of overweight participants, and 5.2% of participants with normal body mass index ($r = 0.68$, $P = 0.02$). When stratified by jobs, stone prevalence significantly increased in retired participants (12.2%) compared to workers (6.8%) ($P < 0.001$). There was no significant difference between urolithiasis and type of drinking water ($P = 0.52$).

Conclusion: The prevalence of urolithiasis in the Vijayapura district is quite common. It seems that the middle-aged population in their third decade of life, those who are overweight, and obese people are at a high risk of developing urolithiasis.

Keywords: Prevalence, Risk Factors, Stones, Sedentary Workers.

Introduction

In the world, urolithiasis is the most common urological disease in living beings. Kidney stone is the most painful and prevalent urological disorder of the urinary system [1]. During the present century, its prevalence has drastically increased in all industrialized countries. About 3–20% of the overall population of the world has the tendency to form one urinary stone during the lifetime of 70 years [2]. Urolithiasis (urinary calculi) formation occurs in the kidney, bladder, and in the urinary tract [3, 4]. Kidney stones are a common urological condition that has been prevalent since ancient times. In India, urolithiasis affects about 2 million people every year [5]. Stone analysis is of great importance to the therapy and metaphylaxis of residual and recurrent stones [6]. The composition of urinary stones in India is different from that in Western countries, where calcium oxalate is the predominant component. It affects about 3% of people of the productive age group [7]. The increasing incidence of crystal deposition diseases in organs such as the urinary tract, kidney, gallstones, etc., in people of all ages affects a considerable number of the total population. It is a major social and economic problem, considering the number of days lost from work and the cost of hospitalization [8].

Urinary stone is one of the oldest and most common afflictions of humans and remains a major public health burden. A large number of people are suffering from urinary stone problems all over the globe. Not only humans, but animals and birds also suffer from urinary stone problems. Generally, three terms, i.e.,

incidence, prevalence, and lifetime prevalence, are frequently used in epidemiological studies of urolithiasis [9-11]. The incidence of stone disease is defined as the number of new stone patients in a given population over a defined period of time. The prevalence is defined as the number of stones present in a screened population at a particular point in time. Finally, the lifetime prevalence is defined as the presence of a stone at any point in a patient's history. Urolithiasis is a global problem spanning all geographic regions, with an estimated annual incidence of 1%, prevalence of 3–5%, and a lifetime risk of 15–25%. Once afflicted, urolithiasis tends to be recurrent in the majority of cases. Fifty percent of kidney stone patients have reappearance within 10 years. In a recent study, the recurrence rates are estimated at about 10% per year, totaling 50% over a 5–10-year period and 75% over 20 years [12].

The incidence of urolithiasis varies in different countries. In India, the “stone belt” occupies parts of Maharashtra, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Punjab, Haryana, Delhi, and the states of the north-east. Fewer occurrences of urinary calculi are found in southern India, which may be due to the regular dietary intake of tamarind. In India, 12% of the people are estimated to have urinary stones, out of which 50% may end up with loss of kidneys or renal damage. Also, nearly 15% of the people of northern India are affected by urinary stones [13]. Singh et al. have reported that the rate of incidence of urolithiasis, particularly staghorn calculi, in Manipur is very high [14]. In recent reports on urolithiasis, it is indicated that in India there is an increased prevalence of urolithiasis in the north-western region.

Methodology

A cross-sectional survey was conducted in June 2021 in Vijayapur district. Data were obtained through direct interviews with participants using an 18-question self-questionnaire, inquiring about demographic data (age, gender, weight, height, location, and occupation), educational level, history of renal stone disease (symptoms, modality of diagnosis, hospital admission, and previous treatment), and risk factors of stone formation such as family history, daily fluid intake, and type of fluid.

Results and Discussion

A total of 300 individuals were interviewed. The overall percentage of those diagnosed with urolithiasis was 5.4%, including 5.6% males and 5.2% females ($P = 0.05$). Of those with stones, 4% were medically treated, 1.4% were hospitalized, and 1.1% were surgically managed for stones. There was a positive linear correlation between the prevalence of stones and participants' age group ($r = 0.87$, $P = 0.01$). More than 80% of participants were highly educated, which did not impact the prevalence of stone formation ($P = 0.12$). Urolithiasis was reported by 7.4% of obese participants, 4.8% of overweight participants, and 5.2% of participants with normal body mass index ($r = 0.68$, $P = 0.02$). When stratified by jobs, stone prevalence significantly increased in retired participants (12.2%) compared to workers (6.8%) ($P < 0.001$). There was no significant difference between urolithiasis and type of drinking water ($P = 0.52$).

The findings of the present study are in agreement with previous studies that reported a higher prevalence of urolithiasis with increasing age and body mass index, as well as a marginal male predominance in stone formation [15-17]. Similar observations regarding the lack of association between educational status, type of drinking water, and urolithiasis prevalence have also been documented in earlier epidemiological studies [18].

Conclusion

The prevalence of urolithiasis in the Vijayapura district is quite common. It seems that the middle-aged population in their third decade of life, those who are overweight, and obese people are at a high risk of developing urolithiasis.

Declarations

Acknowledgments: We gratefully acknowledge all of the people who have contributed to this paper. Special thanks to all the department faculties and participants for their cooperation and constant help for conducting the research study.

Author Contributions: SG: Definition of intellectual content, implementation of study protocol, design of study, statistical analysis and interpretation, literature survey, data collection, data analysis, manuscript preparation, editing, and review manuscript; MM: Concept, design, literature survey, prepared first draft of manuscript, data collection, data analysis; MP: Concept, literature survey, manuscript revision.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Consent to Publish: The authors agree to publish the paper in International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research.

Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: The study was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of BLDEA's Shri B. M. Patil Institute of Nursing Sciences, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India, prior to the commencement of data collection.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed written consent was obtained from all participants involved in the study after explaining the purpose of the research, and confidentiality and anonymity were assured.

Research Content: The research content of this manuscript is original and has not been published elsewhere.

References

1. Thongprayoon, C., Krambeck, A.E. and Rule, A.D. 2020. Determining the true burden of kidney stone disease. *Nature Reviews Nephrology*, 16(12): 736-746.
2. Sorokin, I., Mamoulakis, C., Miyazawa, K., Rodgers, A., Talati, J. and Lotan, Y. 2017. Epidemiology of stone disease across the world. *World Journal of Urology*, 35(9): 1301-1320.
3. Lohiya, A., Kant, S., Kapil, A., Gupta, S.K., Misra, P. and Rai, S.K. 2017. Population-based estimate of urinary stones from Ballabgarh, northern India. *The National Medical Journal of India*, 30(4), 198-200.
4. Marak, A., Shantibala, K., Singh, T.A., Singh, R.K. and Singh, L.S. 2013. Urolithiasis prevalence and related factors in a rural area of Manipur. *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*, 2(4): 956-959.
5. Geraghty, R.M., Cook, P., Walker, V. and Somani, B.K. 2020. Evaluation of the economic burden of kidney stone disease in the UK: A retrospective cohort study with a mean follow-up of 19 years. *BJU International*, 125(4): 586-594.
6. Antonelli, J.A., Maalouf, N.M., Pearle, M.S. and Lotan, Y. 2014. Use of the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey to calculate the impact of obesity and diabetes on cost and prevalence of urolithiasis in 2030. *European Urology*, 66(4): 724-729.
7. Scales, C.D., Jr. 2013. Practice patterns in the management of urinary lithiasis. *Current Urology Reports*, 14(2): 154-157.
8. Daudon, M., Traxer, O., Conort, P., Lacour, B. and Jungers, P. 2006. Type 2 diabetes increases the risk for uric acid stones. *Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, 17(7): 2026-2033.
9. VatcharavongVan, P. and Puttawanchai, V. 2017. Polypharmacy, medication adherence and medication management at home in elderly patients with multiple non-communicable diseases in Thai primary care. *Family Medicine and Primary Care Review*, 19(4): 412-416.
10. Liu, Y., Chen, Y., Liao, B., Luo, D., Wang, K., Li, H. and Zeng, G. 2018. Epidemiology of urolithiasis in Asia. *Asian Journal of Urology*, 5(4): 205-214.
11. Edvardsson, V.O., Indridason, O.S., Haraldsson, G., Kjartansson, O. and Palsson, R. 2013. Temporal trends in the incidence of kidney stone disease. *Kidney International*, 83(1): 146-152.
12. Wang, S., Zhang, Y., Zhang, X., Tang, Y. and Li, J. 2020. Upper urinary tract stone compositions: The role of age and gender. *International Brazilian Journal of Urology*, 46(1): 70-80.
13. Lieske, J.C. 2014. New insights regarding the interrelationship of obesity, diet, physical activity, and kidney stones. *Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, 25(2): 211-212.
14. Singh, P.P., Singh, L.B.K., Prasad, S.N. and Singh, M.G. 1978. Urolithiasis in Manipur (north eastern region of India). Incidence and chemical composition of stones. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 31(9): 1519-1525.
15. Scales, C.D., Jr., Smith, A.C., Hanley, J.M. and Saigal, C.S. 2012. Prevalence of kidney stones in the United States. *European Urology*, 62(1): 160-165.
16. Romero, V., Akpınar, H. and Assimos, D.G. 2010. Kidney stones: A global picture of prevalence, incidence, and associated risk factors. *Reviews in Urology*, 12(2-3): e86-e96.
17. Taylor, E.N., Stampfer, M.J. and Curhan, G.C. 2005. Obesity, weight gain, and the risk of kidney stones. *JAMA*, 293(4): 455-462.

18. Trinchieri, A. 2008. Epidemiology of urolithiasis: An update. *Clinical Cases in Mineral and Bone Metabolism*, 5(2): 101-106.

Citation: Sankappa Gulaganji, Meenaxi Madabhavi and Manjunath Patil. 2025. A Study to Assess the Prevalence of Urolithiasis Among the Sedentary Workers Working in Selected Areas of Vijayapura District, Karnataka. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 9(3): 384-387.

Copyright: ©2025 Sankappa Gulaganji, et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.